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PRESERVATION AND SELECTION OF LOCAL GREEK HONEY
BEES IN THE ISLAND OF GAVDOS/ 'SAFEAGROBEE' PROJECT

*Conservazione e selezione delle api mellifere greche locali nell'isola di Gavdos:
il progetto 'SafeAgroBe'*

Despite the impressive and valuable biodiversity existing in Greece, no effort has been made to preserve a breed or ecotype of a bee or that of the dominant Macedonian breed. The honey bee queen trade and the migratory beekeeping practiced, mainly from North to South in the active period for the swarms, have led to an extensive hybridization of the populations that previously existed in mainland in Greece, as well as the one in the Crete island. We believe, after recent studies, that the populations of Crete is a descendant of the Adami bee, the *Apis mellifera adami* (MOMENI *et al.*, 2021; CHEN *et al.*, 2022), and that efforts need to be undertaken in order firstly to preserve the characteristics of this population and secondly to investigate its resistance behaviour against *Varroa destructor*.

In addition, there are no isolated areas used for controlled matings and Gavdos island is a small island south of Crete, suitable for this purposes. In fact it is the most southwest part of European Union. At the same time it is a paradise for bees: isolated, green and with beekeeping plants, without pesticides. Gavdos could become a small refuge for local varroa-resistant bees, as is being done in other European countries. In order to do so, we firstly monitor the behavior of the bees and their performance during the year, and secondly we reproduce form the varroa resistant colonies based on varroa infestation level, reduced reproduction of varroa and hygienic behaviour (HATJINA *et al.*, 2014; MONDET *et al.*, 2020).

The project in Gavdos island, is supported by the prefecture of Crete, and has a duration of 3 years, with a possible continuation. Later should be

self sustained. The aim, is also to propagate and disseminate the produced queens from Gavdos to all Crete island.

Expected benefits:

- A small shelter of local and selected / resistant bees in Gavdos
- This genetic material will be available to beekeepers in Crete who will later want to bring their queens for fertilization.

At the same time the ‘SafeAgroBee’ (Safeguarding agroecosystem resilience under climate change through efficient pollination and sustainable beekeeping) project is a new 3 year PRIMA project for collaboration in the Mediterranean basin. Its aim is to contribute to adaptation and mitigation of the effects of climate change and other drivers negatively influencing the sustainability and the resilience of the agricultural system in the Mediterranean basin, ensuring the income of farmers and food security; in short ensuring resilience and sustainability. One of the populations to be tested in SafeAgroBee project has the same origin as the one in Gavdos island.

In general, in SafeAgroBee we focus on beekeeping and pollination provided by both wild and managed bees as important drivers in ruling food security and human existence. To this aim, SafeAgroBee will specifically address the following: 1) examine the resilience of bee pollinators (*Apis* and non *Apis* bees) on a changing environment towards pollination services and productivity by a) documenting wild and domesticated bee contribution to the pollination of key crops; b) determining the carrying capacity of several crops as a novel approach for bee productivity and c) by projecting historical climatic data and bee related data in today’s conditions; 2) investigate the adaptability of local bee populations and the application of optimal practices under climate change in order to ensure sustainable beekeeping by monitoring the development and the performance of local populations and their resistance to diseases; 3) support the development of mitigation strategies ensuring the health of the bees and provide advice for the beekeepers by comparing the health and productivity of the honey bee colonies between different agricultural ecosystems and by performing alternative and new strategies to control bee diseases; 4) develop innovative monitoring tools and precision apiculture systems for advanced data acquisition by building on sounds, bee movements and heat detection, also enhancing business potential; 5) test and validate novel models for predicting the health of the bees, as for example the Health Status Index, as well as their productivity in terms of honey and pollination services.

Specific tasks in SafeAgroBee project will focus on the performance of the local populations, also under different varroa treatment conditions and where possible no chemical treatment (as described in BÜCHLER *et al.*, 2020). Chemical varroa treatments, in combination with the chemical input from the

environment (e.g. agricultural products) might lower the susceptibility and the natural immunity of the commercial bee populations (TIHELKA, 2018; HATJINA *et al.*, in preparation). Therefore the synergistic effects of the chemical inputs on honey bee colony sustainability will be investigated.

Both projects, the conservation of local population in Gavdos island and the SafeAgroBee project share some of the aims as well as methodologies.

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